

Research article (Featured theme: Geolinguistic approaches to linguistic patterns in Asia and Africa)

Sibling terms in Asia and Africa: A geolinguistic approach to linguistic patterns

FUKUSHIMA, Chitsuko
University of Niigata Prefecture

Abstract: Sibling terms in Asia and Africa are examined by making new maps, each of which shows detailed distributions of each type of sibling term system. The interpretation of the maps strongly supports a previous interpretation, as follows: (1) Change from Type A to Type B and from Type B to Type C can be inferred from the distributions, (2) Type D and Type E expanded relatively recently, and (3) Type F shows the relic, peripheral distributions.*

Keywords: *Linguistic Atlas of Asia and Africa*; sibling system; linguistic pattern

1. Introduction

The purpose of this paper is to apply a geolinguistic approach to sibling term systems in Asia and Africa. The maps published in the *Linguistic Atlas of Asia and Africa III (LAAA III)* are redrawn here to examine the previous interpretation, made in Fukushima (2023d).

Systems of sibling terms are described using three criteria, which are based on distinctions of (1) relative age, (2) sex, and (3) relative sex (Matsumoto 2006 and Murdock 1968), and there is a variety of systems, as shown in Table 1. Types A to E are based on distinctions of relative age and sex. Type A (undifferentiated sibling type) has just one term for ‘sibling’. Type B (relative age type) has two terms, for ‘elder sibling’ and ‘younger sibling’. Type C (skewed age type) has three terms, for ‘elder brother’, ‘elder sister’, and ‘younger sibling’. Type D (age/sex type) has four terms, for ‘elder brother’, ‘elder sister’, ‘younger brother’, and ‘younger sister’. Type E (sex type or brother/sister type) has two terms, for ‘brother’ and ‘sister’. Types F to FE make distinctions of relative sex, which are often combined with other distinctions. These

FUKUSHIMA, Chitsuko. 2024. Sibling terms in Asia and Africa: A geolinguistic approach to linguistic patterns. *Studies in Geolinguistics* 4: 145–155. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13948605>

* This work was supported by Tokyo University of Foreign Studies, April 2020–March 2023 ILCAA Joint Research Project: Studies in Asian and African Geolinguistics (jrp000256), with Mitsuaki Endo as coordinator; and JSPS KAKENHI grant number JP19K00555.

types are typological and regarded as linguistic patterns, each of which is expected to show a different geographical distribution. Therefore, to enable the visual representation of the systems' distributions, a symbol was assigned to each system type before the researchers of each language or language group in the project made the separate linguistic maps.

Table 1 Types of sibling term systems (Fukushima 2023a, 2023c)

	Type	Relative age	Sex	Relative sex	Symbol
A	Undifferentiated sibling type				○
B	Relative age type	+			—
C	Skewed age type	+	+		▽
D	Age/sex type	++	++		□
E	Sex type (brother/sister type)		+		◇
F	Relative sex type			+	⊕
FB	Relative sex/age type	+		+	/
FC	Relative sex/skewed age type	+	+	+	▽
FD	Relative sex/age/sex type	++	++	+	▱
FE	Relative sex/sex type		+	+	⋈

When I first examined the geographical variation of sibling term systems in Asia and Africa as part of the *LAAA III* project in 2023, the maps were not ready for online superposition; thus, I used the rate (percentage) of each system in a language or language family. I could count the numbers of each system by reading the maps or the descriptions of each map. First, a map including pie charts was made using the percentages. See Figure 1.

Fig. 1 Types of sibling term systems in Asia and Africa (Fukushima 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d)

Fig. 2 Type A (Fukushima 2023b, 2023c, 2023d)

Fig. 3 Type B (Fukushima 2023b, 2023c, 2023d)

Fig. 4 Type C (Fukushima 2023b, 2023c, 2023d)

Fig. 5 Type D (Fukushima 2023b, 2023c, 2023d)

Fig. 6 Type E (Fukushima 2023b, 2023c, 2023d)

Fig. 7 Type F (Fukushima 2023b, 2023c, 2023d)

Next, maps showing the variation of each system were made. See Figures 2–7 above. Based on these maps, the following interpretation was made (Fukushima 2023d). In this paper, I will verify this interpretation using new maps.

1. Change from Type A to Type B and from Type B to Type C can be inferred from the distributions.
2. Type D and Type E expanded relatively recently.
3. Type F shows the relic, peripheral distributions.

2. Method and results

Separate original maps of sibling term systems were made by experts on specific languages or language groups in Asia and Africa, using ArcGIS online. They were published in the *Linguistic Atlas of Asia and Africa III* (Fukushima et al. 2023). The maps of sibling term systems of each language or language group were superimposed online to produce a map of sibling term systems across Asia and Africa (see Figure 8). The color for each language or language group was decided beforehand; see Table 2.

Based on this map, maps of each type were made by deleting maps that did not show that type, and also deleting symbols of types other than the type at hand. The new maps (Figures 9–14) thus produced are shown and discussed in the following section.

Fig. 8 Sibling term systems in Asia and Africa: all types

Table 2 The language groups and colors (made by Satoko Shirai)

Language group	Color	Language group	Color
Ainu	Red	Korean	Light blue
Andamanese and language isolates (South Asia)	Black	Kra-Dai	Navy
Austroasiatic	Green	Kx'a (Kalahari Basin Area)	Light blue
Austronesian	Orange	Mongolic	Green
Caucasian	Light blue	Niger-Congo	Navy
Chukotko-Kamchatkan	Black	Nilo-Saharan	Green
Dravidian	Red	Semitic	Brown
Hmong-Mien	Orange	Sinitic	Red
Indo-Aryan and Nuristani (South Asia)	Navy	Tibeto-Burman	Brown
Iranian	Orange	Tungusic	Orange
Japonic	Green	Turkic	Light blue
Khoe-Kwadi (Kalahari Basin Area)	Brown	Tuu (Kalahari Basin Area)	Orange
		Uralic	Light blue

Fig. 9 Type A: Undifferentiated sibling type

Fig. 10 Type B: Relative age type

Fig. 11 Type C: Skewed age type

Fig. 12 Type D: Age/sex type

Fig. 13 Type E: Brother/sister type

Fig. 14 Type F: Relative sex type

3. Discussion

If we compare these maps with the maps introduced in Section 1 (Figures 2–7), we find that the new maps show detailed, actual distributions of each type: whether the distribution is dense or sporadic, how it expanded, and so forth. Let me examine each map.

Figure 9 shows that Type A is found in the vast area of Southeast Asia and Africa but is rather scattered. Figure 10 shows that Type B is found in areas nearby to Type

Fig. 15 Type B focusing on Southeast Asia

Fig. 16 Type C focusing on Southeast Asia

A, and its distribution is rather dense. Figure 11 shows that Type C is found all over Asia, that its distribution in Indochina is especially dense, and that it is also found in Africa. Also see Figures 15 and 16, the maps of Types B and C, which focus on Southeast Asia. Type C is found in Java and Vietnam, and you can see the routes of Type C in the Tibeto-Burman area, while the distribution of Type B can be seen to be surrounding that of Type C; thus, Type C is newer than Type B. Overall, the change from Type A (undifferentiated sibling type) to Type B (relative age type) and to Type C (skewed age type) is probable as the direction of lexical change, which is supported by the distributions of these three types.

Figure 12 shows that Type D (age/sex type) clearly spread from China, through several routes to South Asia and to Europe. See Figure 17, which focuses on East Asia and shows the routes more clearly. There are a couple of locations in Africa where Type D is used, where it likely developed from Types A, B, and C, maybe due to contact with the brother/sister type.

Fig 17 Type D: Age/sex type: focus on East Asia

Figure 13 shows that Type E (brother/sister type) is only found in the western part of the map, which suggests that this type spread from the west.

Figures 12 and 13 suggest that Types D and E spread rather recently, making inroads into the areas of the other types' distributions.

Figure 14 shows that Type F (relative sex type) is found, sporadically, on the peripheries of Asia and Africa, especially in the eastern and southern edges of Eurasia and also in parts of Africa. Many different languages and language families in these areas have this type, suggesting that it may be the oldest type in the area.

4. Conclusion

The newly-made maps strongly support the previous interpretation and illustrate the distributions more clearly.

Notes for copyrights

The members of the 2020–2023 project involved in the investigation of the sibling data are the following linguists: ONO Chikako (Chukotko-Kamchatkan), FUKAZAWA Mika (Ainu), FUKUSHIMA Chitsuko (Japonic), FUKUI Rei (Korean), YAGI Kenji (Sinitic), TAGUCHI Yoshihisa and TANG Baiyan (Hmong-Mien), HIRANO Ayaka, ENDO Mitsuaki, and TOMITA Aika (Kra-Dai), KURABE Keita, EBIHARA Shiho, IWASA Kazue, SHIRAI Satoko, and SUZUKI Hiroyuki (Tibeto-Burman), SHIMIZU Masaaki and MINEGISHI Makoto (Austroasiatic), UTSUMI Atsuko (Austronesian), MATSUMOTO Ryo (Tungusic and Uralic), SAITÔ Yoshio (Mongolic and Turkic), YOSHIOKA Noboru (South Asia), KODAMA Nozomi (Dravidian), IWASAKI Takamasa (Iranian), NAGATO Youichi (Semitic), NAKAO Shuichiro (Nilo-Saharan), SHINAGAWA Daisuke and KOMORI Junko (Niger-Congo), and KIMURA Kimihiko and NAKAGAWA Hiroshi (Kalahari Basin Area). I express my sincere thanks to the contributors.

References

- Fukushima, Chitsuko (2023a) Overview of the system of ‘sibling’ terms. Paper presented at the 6th meeting of the ILCAA Joint Research Project: Studies in Asian and African Geolinguistics, Tokyo University of Foreign Studies and online, 25–26 March.
- Fukushima, Chitsuko (2023b) The geographical variation of the system of ‘sibling’ terms in Asia and Africa. Paper presented at the 10th Congress of the International Society for Dialectology and Geolinguistics (SIDG 10), Bucharest, Romania, 4–8 September.
- Fukushima, Chitsuko (2023c) Overview of the system of ‘sibling’ terms. In: Chitsuko Fukushima, Satoko Shirai, Mika Fukazawa, Hiroyuki Suzuki, and Mitsuaki Endo (eds.) *Linguistic Atlas of Asia and Africa III*, 3–8. Tokyo: Geolinguistic Society of Japan. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10223731>
- Fukushima, Chitsuko (2023d) Geographical variation of systems of sibling terms in Asia and Africa. *Dialectologia et Geolinguistica* 31: 41–54. De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/dialect-2023-0003>
- Fukushima, Chitsuko, Satoko Shirai, Mika Fukazawa, Hiroyuki Suzuki, and Mitsuaki Endo (eds.) (2023) *Linguistic Atlas of Asia and Africa III*. Tokyo: Geolinguistic Society of Japan. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10223731>
- Matsumoto, Katsumi [松本克己] (2006) *Sekai Gengo eno Shiza: Rekishi Gengogaku to Gengo Ruikeiron* 『世界言語への視座：歴史言語学と言語類型論』 [Outlook on world languages: Historical linguistics and linguistic typology], 391–443. Tokyo: Sanseido.

Murdock, George Peter (1968) Patterns of sibling terminology. *Ethnology* 7(1): 1–24.
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/3772805>

Publication history

Date received: 31 August 2024

Date accepted: 17 September 2024